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Examining Leadership Behavior during COVID-19: A Phenomenological Study of the Contingent Approach

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ABSTRACT

In this period, the world is being confronted with the world's worst epidemic challenge, which has never seen before. It destroyed millions of jobs and shook the world's most powerful economies. Thousands of people have lost their jobs as a result of the pandemic. The phenomenon that is happening these days, in which organizations are concerned with financial gain to make the continue striving, organizations are being faced with the current COVID-19 pandemic. Because of the COVID 19 wave, domestic economies and businesses suffered a serious setback. The study's main goal was to discover an emergence of situational leadership, also known as new normal leadership, among corporate sectors in the Karachi during the COVID-19 pandemic. The study used a qualitative research design to explain people's living experiences with a particular phenomenon or human condition. Themes were extracted in the data analysis using transcriptions, codes, and triangulations of the data gathered. According to the findings, New Normal Leadership is described as: (1) the ability to change while remaining committed; (2) being an efficient instructional decision-maker; and (3) a leader who is a good planner, attentive, and initiator. This also create it a contest for management to develop proper working guidelines and procedures, as well as promote creative work performance, in order to maintain the organization's outcome and profitability.

Keywords: Leadership; Contingent Plan; Data Driven Culture; Social Distancing, COVID-19.

1. INTRODUCTION

In this period, the world is confronted with the world's worst epidemic challenge, which has never been seen before. It destroyed millions of jobs and shook the world's most powerful economies. Thousands of people have lost their jobs as a result of the pandemic. Organizations are putting workers in the driver's seat when it comes to managing their shifts and working styles. The COVID 19 outbreak has given the organization the opportunity to adopt a variety of strategies to protect their employees from this deadly disease while still achieving their organizational goals. It provides a variety of work options, such as the workstation as a point of contact and a crowd of persons is a danger factor that necessitates anticipating the transmission effect (MENKES, 2020). Because of the COVID 19 wave, domestic economies and businesses suffered a serious setback. The World Health Organization (WHO) has been publishing guidelines and precautionary measures to deal with the "new normal scenarios" on a regular basis. As a control measure to time box the virus, the majority of affected republics have imposed a fractional or full lockdown of their economies (Lau et al., 2020; Remuzzi & Remuzzi, 20). A large number of Standard Operating Procedures and criteria are being developed and implemented around the world to combat COVID 19. The COVID outbreak wreaked havoc on various sectors of the global economy, particularly the travel and tourism industries, which were severely impacted by the deadly and contagious virus.

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Various measures have been used by governments and authorities around the world, ranging from physical social separation, restrictions on free movement, and the closure of non-essential companies and undertakings to the lockdown of entire cities, industrial and social hubs in various parts of the world. As the pandemic spreads, so do the measures taken by governments to combat it. The majority of governments are attempting to control the virus's spread and minimize its economic impact by implementing a number of measures. During this epidemic period, the idea of working from home and flexible working styles became more prevalent. Human Resources departments are developing and implementing a variety of tools and strategies in order to ensure that organizational goals are met. The human resources department's role has become increasingly important in meeting and ensuring the implementation of attendance policies and procedures. It should not only be in accordance with the SOPs of the respective governments and higher authorities, but also with the organizational processes and guidelines. The current COVID-19 eruption has demonstrated how quickly companies must respond to rapidly evolving HR-related issues (McCulloch, 2020; Sylvers & Foldy, 2020; Wei & Wong, 2020).

The COVID 19 has had an impact on the development of the Pakistani economy as well. Individuals in the republic became even more vulnerable to scarcity as a result of the pandemic, and those who were already vulnerable were pushed further below the poverty line. It caused the country's economy to contract and its growth rate to slow. The unemployment rate is still higher than expected. The Pakistan government has released a number of Standard Operating Procedures for organizations and businesses relating shift management, social distancing, working on reduced strength, compressed working hours, and so on. They released a set of guidelines and procedures that must be adhered to and implemented in the company. The phenomenon that is happening these days, in which organizations are concerned with financial gain to make the continue striving, organizations are confronted with the existing COVID-19 pandemic. That also creates it a test for administration to develop suitable working guidelines and procedures, as well as promote creative work performance, in order to maintain the organization's outcome and profitability.

Acquiring the identical output by utilizing the reduced work strength is the great challenge for organizational leaders and managers. Now it's created the excessive pressure on the Human Resources Professionals to maintain and survive in this low growth economy period. Pakistani organizations and companies cannot avoid this universal situation. To cope up and face the desired challenges, they must redesign and innovate their work structure and working environment. The aim of the research is to explore the role of leaders in this pandemic phenomena, how they managed and moved on their organization with this rapidly varying environment as well boost up the morale of their employees, one side demonstrated the new normal leadership to face situations successfully and on the other hand acquire the organizational aims subsequently.

According to above mentioned problem, the purpose of this study to provide the batter understanding about the leadership skills required to enhance the employee's motivation during pandemic. In order to serve the above purpose, the study highlighted the main issue that need to be addressed, i.e., how the leadership skills demonstrated by the leaders in organization during the crises of COVID 19 to achieve the organizational goals and objectives?

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

During the COVID 19 span, this chapter specifically discusses the literature of leadership styles and their role, how their decisions impacted on organizational growth, further what are the strategies and tactics they developed and implemented to face this pandemic situation. According to the World Health Organization, the COVID 19 virus was discovered in Wuhan, China, in January 2020. (WHO). The CORONA virus was extremely difficult to avoid. Its growth was accelerated even further by the Chinese New Year travel and tour boom. COVID-19 was declared a pandemic by WHO on March 11, 2020, as the disasterblowout to more countries outer of China (WHO, 2020). Since the pandemic was announced, the global climate has changed dramatically. Lockdown, social distancing, work from home, flexible work arrangements, and many other mechanisms and terms are being planned and applied all over the world. People all over the world have embraced a modern way of living and altered their social habits in order to prepare for the pandemic. They chose to keep neighborhood movements to a bare minimum, and they stick to it. When restrictions on group movement and congregation are used at different stages of the disease, the outcomes are drastically different (Hatchett, Mecher, & Lipsitch, 2007).

The current COVID-19 eruption has revealed how rapidly companies must react to Human Resources-related issues (McCulloch, 2020; Sylvers & Foldy, 2020; Wei & Wong, 2020). Robinson (2009) provided advice about how to handle workers during tough times and keep them motivated and engaged during transitions. Employees who work in virtual environments have characterized an emotional state of professional and social segregation as a result of a lack of sense of identity, companionship, and confidence that occurs during physical encounters and social interactions. Several republics have also sealed their borders to prevent the virus from spreading across continents (Ghosh, Brindisi, Shahabi, Mackenzie, & Andrew, 2020). According to Business Insider (Kaplan, Frias, & MefallJohnsen, 2020), the majority of countries are putting in place procedures to slow the spread of COVID19, ranging from nationwide quarantines to institute closures.

This pandemic has had a significant impact on the global economy. To prevent the deadly virus from spreading, most countries have closed their borders and stopped trading with other countries. The situation has put a lot of pressure on the company to keep and involve its staff when working with minimal resources. Employees, on the other hand, are demoralized as a result of low efficiency, work instability, and termination as well as retrenchment problems. Because of COVID 19, the business world has taken on a new lease on life. The impact of the corona virus on organizational efficiency has been observed to be disrupted.

The primary goal of lockdown is isolation, which separates people who have been diagnosed with this deadly disease from those who have not (Brooks et al., 2020). Leadership styles are becoming increasingly important in order to meet the demands and desires of employees, which are the as a result of socio-demographic changes and requirements. It becomes apparent that, in pandemic situations of extreme change, a focus on identification with the leader is required in order to build confidence, where subordinates must combine respect for hierarchy with responding to a crisis that necessitates cooperation, thus stressing responsiveness to the leader's guidance.

2.1 Leadership

Leaders are person who are the real drivers of organization, they create organizational long term strategic plan, goals and objectives, design the process and polices, make them implemented by their followers to achieve organizational aims and objectives. In a time of crisis, the most important trait of leadership is good communication. In general, leadership treatments are successful during times of crisis, although it is clear that such crisis situations would almost certainly necessitate prioritization of different leadership skills. Leadership, according to (Kargas, & Varoutas, 2015), refers to a person's ability to control the majority of a group of people to accomplish an objective or collection of goals. As a result, leadership is about duplicating with transformative abilities and competences that a leader exhibits to influence a group of people to achieve a vision or a created set of objectives. In addition to replicating with transformation and development of vision for motivating people (Cruz-Milán, et al., 2016), leadership is about duplicating with transform and vision creation for inspiring individuals (Cruz-Milán, et al., 2016). According to (Bipath, 2012), it entails demonstrating the way that will entice people to work enthusiastically by fostering peace in the pursuit of a common objective. It is true to say that the efficacy of leadership within an organization is determined by how individuals behave and function in terms of achieving goals successfully, and good leaders are those who are able to achieve this goal.

2.1.1 Transformational Leadership styles

According to Kelly (2005), the most powerful leadership style in a crisis is Transformational leadership is a type of leadership that responds quickly to change in the face of a crisis. According to Bass (1985), a transformational leader possesses qualities that allow him or her to solve a crisis while also preventing some of the crisis's negative consequences. The idealized influence of leaders on their followers is the first quality of a transformational leadership style. Transformational leaders should set an example for their followers in terms of core beliefs, convictions, and ethical standards that can apply during a crisis. Transformational leaders focus on the people behaviors, beliefs and attitude. They transformed their approach. Under this approach leader motivate, encourage and make followers inspired to grow and acquire the organizational objectives. These involve linking a follower's sense of self to the organization's mission and common identity; inspiring followers by being a role model; challenging followers to take greater control of their work; and identifying followers' strengths and weaknesses so the leader can assign tasks that maximize their success.

2.1.2 Transactional leadership style

According to Zohar and Luria (2004), a transactional leadership style would have a positive impact on the result when coping with a crisis because it allows the organization to carry out more complicated operational processes. This means that the transformational leader is needed to respond to emergencies, while the transactional leader is needed to carry out the decision(s) made by the transformational leader. It is more concerned about the organizational functions. Under such type of leadership targets and objectives are achieve by offering financial and non-financial rewards. Transactional leaders are more concerned about the organizational SOPs and procedures rather than forward thinking.

2.2. Employee Performance

According to Armstrong & Baron (1998: 159), performance is about how to do efforts and the outcomes attained from the effort. Performance is the outcome of effort that has a solid connection with the organization's strategic goals and objectives, satisfaction of customer and contribution in economy. Trend which demonstrates how healthy he/she is executing his/her job, work and tasks is called staff performance. Staff productivity is counted through their performance. Staff performance can be achieved through operative shift arrangements and work from home in period of COVID 19. To get higher performance one will have exert greater efforts (Baker, 1998; Jensen, 1998; Murphy, 1998). Employee performance is assumed to be completion of a promise in a specify ways that reliefs the employees from all responsibilities and accountabilities. Managing performance of employee is a set of actions designed to ensure that a business gets the performance it requires from its people (Mathis & Jackson, 2008). According to Rahman and Kistyanto (2019), performance is an achievement of work performance, both in quality and quantity, that has been carried out based on the work objectives that the organization has defined. Organizations are much focusing for improving the employee performance especially in COVID 19 period. The organization can get the lesson form the fear of leaving the highly skilled and talented employees to move to the competitors (Blinder, 1991; Krueger, 1991; & Bishop, 1991).

A behavior reflecting what has been learned by the workers or the types of training workers has got in work place is called the employee performance, it comprises the results of the psychological and mental abilities (Faiza and Nazir, 2015). Worker Performance is an impression that is progressively wide spread between researchers of management sciences, as worker performance is necessary to organization and individual himself. Staff Performance donates to the whole improvement of the procedures of the companies predominantly in relations of competence and output (Abualoush et al., 2018a). Moreover, Employee performance has connection to the actions and responsibilities staffs transmit in efficient and effective manner, and it also directives

how ample staffs pay to the companies and amongst the offerings of staffs are productivity number, attendance at work, and helpful approach (Abualoush et al., 2018b). In addition, the monetary or non-monetary results of the staff which are narrowly connected to the act and achievement of the companies is also replicated by staff performance (Anitha, 2014). In respects to the idea of staff performance, it is quantifiable by means of various procedures (Faiza and Nazir, 2015), and in general, performance includes what is completed or not complete by employees. This involves the complete result or achievement of an individual throughout precise phases of responsibility as opposite to the prearranged and recognized normal of effort and goals or conditions (Abualoush et al., 2018; Pawirosumarto et al., 2017). Performance is the artifact of the ability of worker, increased with backing and exertion. Hence, decrease or absence of one factor will source reduction in performance (Pawirosumarto et al., 2017).

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The method used in this study teaches us how to collect and process data. This chapter gives an overview of the general research methods and techniques used in this study, as well as the specific approaches and tools used in data collection and analysis.

3.1. Research Design

In this analysis, the phenomenological approach was used to use qualitative data in the form of narrations. The participants were asked to participate in a focus group discussion to explore their perspectives on their lived experiences as organization. The approach was phenomenological since it sought to explain their feelings and experiences. This research will explore the leadership styles during the pandemic COVID 19 phenomena in organizations in Pakistan.

3.2. Population

The extent of this research is all organizations and companies situated at Karachi. All manufacturing, and services companies' management cadre staffs are selected as population for this research. There are five big industrial zones are existing in Karachi. Federal Area, Sindh Industrial Trading state (SITE), Korangi Industrial Area (KIA), Ahsanabad, and Port Qasim. Each zone has number of organizations. Further the services sector is stretched among two main areas i.e. I.I. Chundrigir and Shakra-e-Faisal Karachi. All management cadre staff, both male and female, either probationary or confirmed employees will be population of this research.

3.3. Sample

As this is qualitative study so a few organizations will be selected and their employees/staff will be interviewed. When sample is collected from population without any favoritism and everyone has equal chances to be selected. It must be representative of the population.

3.4. Data Gathering

The following are essential for a smooth data collection flow: The researchers meticulously followed the following procedures:

1. The participants were given an overview of the study by the researchers. told them that their involvement was entirely up to them. They had been
2. They were given the option of participating in the study or not.
3. The interview guidelines were provided in advance to assist them in preparing for the interview on the day of the interview. The interview guideline helped in the provision of information-dense interviews.

3.5. Validity

For all qualitative studies, the validity of the study results is crucial (Wang & Lien, 2013). Validity is the foundation on which the credibility of a study finding is built in qualitative research. It is critical to the accuracy of the data. Validity refers to how well the researchers have captured the phenomenon (Morse, 2015).

3.6. Trustworthiness

A lot of time spent on evaluating the surroundings, talking to the interviewees, and building relationships with them. On the basis of knowledge of the study, leaning to the situations and cultures of the participants, and being able to spot any bias or distortion that would affect the data, the participants' trust was built, and they were invited to remark on and offer information.

3.6.1. Credibility

Establishing the credibility in qualitative research is much more difficult than the quantitative research however it has been ensured by applying the following factors, which are as follows!

- Adoption of appropriate, well recognized research methods
- Development of early familiarity with culture of participating organizations
- Random sampling of individuals serving as informants
- Triangulation via use of different methods, different types of informants and different sites

3.6.2. Transferability

Although transferability is difficult in qualitative research because of variation of respondents and nature of research. However, one of the researchers, Gross, writes of the "multiple environments" in which the phenomenon of interest takes place and believes the study should provide a "baseline understanding" with which the results of subsequent work should be compared. They provided some baseline about the Leadership Styles and Traits and concluded the skill sets of leaders required to be faced and cope up this pandemic new normal situation.

3.6.3. Dependability

Dependability can be acquired by overlapping methods, so they used both semi structured interview and focus group interview to ensure the dependability in their research. The research design was successfully implemented. Moreover, they have described in details about the data collection methods. At conclusion they evaluated their results in order to acquire the reflective appraisal of

research.

3.6.4. Conformability

The conformability may be enhanced by comparing the results of research with the researcher’s predisposition. Further by applying audit trail method, conformability is improved. In this research the researchers have not designed the audit trail diagram but they presented their step by step worked to make it conformability.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The detail analysis has been performed on the basis of the data collected from the samples through distributed questionnaire. The data analysis has been performed by using various software i.e. MS Excel and SPSS etc.

4.1 Data Analysis

The code and theme procedures have been used in analyzing and interpreting the narratives of the respondents (see, Figure 1). The researcher abstracts the themes from the code. After which, the data processed will be triangulated and checked by the respondents. Research begins with the research questions described above; preliminarily we are to search the employees who are working in organizational management cadre, then we are to construct an interview guide to assess informants. Due to the rapid increase in Covid-19 instances, we are intending to conduct interviews on Zoom or Google Meet or some other online programme that offers recording having the duration about 20 to 30 minutes. Further it has been transcribed these interview by using the recoding of the interview. The open coding methodology outlined by Strauss and Corbin (1990) is expected to be used to develop the codes. What informants say will be interpreted in order to have a better understanding of their views and attitudes regarding investment decision-making. Statements will be scrutinized using a variety of codes. For example, first-order codes are a link between numerous codes that lead to derived second-order codes.

Figure 1: Manual Coding Process

Source: Author’s work.

The core textual data acquired through interviews will be subjected to content analysis. After that, the textual data will be transcribed, coded, and themes will be retrieved from the transcripts (see, Table 1).

Table 1: Theme Extractions

Respondent Views	Theme	Extraction
Yes, the resumption of duties after the pandemic is associated with the new normal situation, using of mask, gloves , applying sanitizer on	SOPs, Strategies, Tactics, Screening Programs, mask, gloves & social distancing	New Normal Situation

Respondent Views	Theme	Extraction
hand frequently and keeping the social distance at workplace.		
They stated his leadership has done great role during Pandemic not only to achieve organization objectives but also focused on their employee's moral keep high. Their leadership is much adoptable , always ready to adopt various tools, strategies and tactics according to varied situations. Their leadership is visionary and democratic in style.	Organizational Objectives, Early Adoptable, Policies and Procedures, change management	Change Agent & Adoptability
Their leaders make decision on the basis of fact and figures . As the nature of organization requires rapid and frequent decision which followed by the leadership during this pandemic situation. He quoted one of the example" once the ABC organization presented fake data to acquire rating, upon reveling the actual position their leadership took concrete and strict decision to revoke the organization rating rapidly". His leadership also took some harsh decision inorder to meet the need of business to face and cope the pandemic situation. Organizational leaders evaluate and consider all necessary factors while taking decisions related numerous issues. He also explained he witnessed that "his leaders are used to take responsibility of all shortcomings and drops of his decision rather than making the blame on the employees".	Data Culture, Trend Analysis, Factors Analysis, Production Target, Responsibility	Decision Making
His leadership has shown excellent planning and implementation skills while the pandemic running on. These are not only associated with COVID 19 situation but also having strong grips and skillsets to prepare the plan and implement it accordingly over the time and situations. They also focused on contingent and alternate plans in case of failure of master plan. One more important point presented in interview, his leadership always support in the development of young leaders, they believe that young leaders can make the future	Contingent Plan, Credit Acknowledgement, Reward	Planning & Implementation

Respondent Views	Theme	Extraction
of organizations. Another leadership skillset is explained by interviewee, acknowledgment of credit, his leadership always encourages to their employees to take decision and in return employees are rewarded and acknowledged for their great deeds in organization.		

4.1.1 New Normal Situation

The phrase "new normal" isn't exactly new; it was coined after World War II. According to a study, leadership in the new normal is a type of leadership in which the author identifies good to exceptional leadership qualities in progenitors like George Washington and Abraham Lincoln, effectively describing the essence of leadership. The term "new normal" was coined by the Urban Dictionary in 2009. being after a significant change has taken place. After a given incident, it replaces the accepted, habitual, and typical condition. The new normal has got much popular among corporate sector specially with the emergence of COVID 19 Pandemic surged in last year. The respondent views supported the new normal implementation and its role in the pandemic situation. Since the resumption of duties after the uplifting the Lock Down situation, there are so many new strategies and tactics have been designed and implement to keep the workplace safe and free of COVID 19. Washing and Sanitizing the hand back to back, keeping the distance at workplace, work from home and applying and wearing the masks while going outside are a few tools have been implemented to minimize the effect of this fatal virus. Employees screening program are also introduced while entering in the organization to reduce the spreading of the COVID 19 in workplace.

A few associated activities, identified in new normal, are as under!

- Standard Operating Procedure (SOPs)
- Masks
- Gloves
- Sanitizer
- Tunnels
- Screening Program

4.1.2 Adoptability

The role of leaders in Pandemic has got much important in maintaining and sustaining the organization. The organizational leaders have great pressure to not only acquire their organizational objectives and goals as well to keep their employee's morale high. Moreover, providing the healthy and safe workplace free from the fatal disease, to all employees in organization. The interview revealed that in most of the organization leaders adopted the change and new normal situation rapidly to face and overcome the issues related to the COVID 19 pandemic. Leaders at organization also designed and implement various innovative strategies i.e. reduced working hours, online/work from home concept as well flexible shift system. They also performed rapid environmental scanning and adopted and implemented the various modern practices need to curb the impact of this fatal virus i.e. COVID 19.

4.1.3. Decisions Making

The term decision making refers, selecting the best strategy from the available options. While interview, most of the respondent supported their leader took great decision while pandemic period. They created the Data driven culture in their organization. All the decisions are adopted and implemented on the basis of fact and figures. Trend analysis are performed to acquire the impact of their decision on organizations. ERP and other software are utilized to maintain the data in organizations. Involvement of young leader are also important in their organization. Senior leaders listen the voice of young leaders. Young leader's development programs are also implemented in their organizations. Every decision related to pandemic shared and communicated with all stake holders. Their leadership are having courage and dare to take responsibility of pros and cons of their decisions. Respondent also revealed that the leaders are, in organization, also accountable for their decisions. They are stick on the consequences of their verdicts and associated results. Organizational leaders evaluate and consider all necessary factors while taking decisions related numerous issues.

4.1.4 Planning & Implementation

The role of leaders in planning and its implementation is imperative for the organizational success. Their leadership has shown excellent planning and implementation skills while the pandemic running on. These are not only associated with COVID 19 situation but also having strong grips and skill sets to prepare the plan and implement it accordingly over the time and situations. They also focused on contingent and alternate plans in case of failure of master plan. One more important point presented in interview, his leadership always support in the development of young leaders, they believe that young leaders can make the future of organizations. Another leadership skill set is explained by interviewee, acknowledgment of credit, his leadership always encourages

to their employees to take decision and in return employees are rewarded and acknowledged for their great deeds in organization.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Under the research we have evaluated the role of leadership while the COVID 19 pandemic being occurred. As the world has got paradigm shift from normal life to new normal situations. The skill sets of leadership as well their competence level also need to be redefined. It has been extracted that we must adapt to the new normal; if the disease cannot be confined, we must live with it because viruses are always mutating (Denworth, 2020). Given the impending new normal post-COVID-19, a rethinking of corporate from the regular standpoint. Further the organizational leader's adoptability and change management abilities are also evaluated. "The willingness and ability to modify behaviors, feelings, and beliefs in response to external demands" is how adaptability is defined (McArdle, Waters, Briscoe, & Hall, 2007, p.248). Organizational performance and survival are understood to be dependent on adaptation and creativity (Holtkamp, 2014). The leaders need to adopt and cope up with the external changes. Additional the decision making during the period of pandemic has also been extracted. Leaders make decisions on a daily basis. According to Ejimobo (2015) The fundamental role of leadership is decision-making, and people always identify leadership in business and politics with making smart decisions and a strong emphasis on being the group's leader. Results revealed that their leadership are keen to take decision which are based on facts and figures. Moreover, each and every factors are evaluated while making the decisions in organizations. At last leaders one more skill, planning and implementation, of leadership are discussed while implementing the COVID 19 strategies. The respondent shown that their leaders planned and implemented various SOPs in organization to reduce the contraction of virus. During these challenging times, the formation of a situational leadership termed New Normal Leadership has been truly demonstrated by organizations, even in a single minute, day by day, and wherever they are, to promote quality of the leadership in the country. A few concepts are extracted from the interviews of employees who are working in corporate sector. Leaders in these days are much adoptable and ready to adopt the various changes occurred in external environment. Further derived that the leaders grabbed timely decision making in the pandemic era by exploring all necessary factors and data driven culture. A good planner, vigilant, and initiator is an excellent leader. Most of the leaders was prepared excellent plan and took various initiatives to overcome and curb the impact of fatal virus on their organizations. These ideas were backed up by a number of experts in the field. On the basis of results revealed and extracted from the interviews, the organizational leaders should adopt the various innovative and modern SOPs in their organization to reduce the impact of COVID 19, further the timely decision can also be the reasons to acquire the competitive advantage in this cut-throat era.

Ethical approval

All international standards have been adopted and compliance.

Informed consent

The study was conducted with equal participation by all authors.

Conflicts of interests

The authors declare that there are no conflicts of interests.

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Data and materials availability

All data associated with this study are present in the paper.

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